

Evaluating Pavement Condition Index and Maintenance Management using Artificial Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT:

The pavement condition index (PCI) calculates pavement conditions based on current distresses. In traditional PCI calculation, a visual inspection method collects field data such as distresses and stiffness. Data helps anticipate PCI values, a lengthy and difficult process. This research aims to create a simple, adaptable model that shows how PCIs, distresses, and stiffness relate. Artificial neural networks (ANN) forecast PCI values for various parts, eliminating manual labour and specialized procedures. Based on distresses, the PCI estimates pavement conditions. For typical PCI intentions, a visual inspection device collects field data such as distresses and stiffness. The data allows time-consuming and complicated PCI estimation. This study seeks to construct a simple, extensible model that links PCIs, distresses, and rigidity. ANN prediction part PCI values, eliminating the need for manual labour and specialized technologies.

Keywords: Pavement maintenance management, PCI, distress, AI, road condition and safety.

Suggested Citation: S. Abbas, A.A. Khalil, M.S. Ali, S. Sultana, S.H.H.Shah, "Evaluating Pavement Condition Index and Maintenance Management using Artificial Neural Networks," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(2), pp. 224-232, Mar-Apr 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).15](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).15)

INTRODUCTION

Pavement is a structural element of road that utilized for the easiness of travelling. Therefore, the maintenance of pavement is a necessary part of transportations system. The main failure of road is distress, so the distress analysis can be done by using pavement condition index. The objective of this study to make a relationship between distresses of road and severity. To conduct this investigation, a Pavement condition index model will be utilized. In contrast to the stone highways of antiquity, contemporary highways are neither designed or constructed with perpetual durability, mostly driven by economic considerations. Roads in the majority of Pakistani regions are typically constructed with a lifespan of 15 to 20 years. Nevertheless, through consistent and diligent maintenance, the lifespan of the design can be considerably prolonged. The expense of rebuilding a deteriorated road due to negligence is usually three times more than maintaining a regularly maintained route [1-3].

The condition of a pavement is assessed through the analysis of data that quantifies various factors, including rideability, surface deterioration, structural integrity, and skid resistance. Numerous approaches employed in the NBIS, PCI, and LTPP necessitate the collection of point data in situ. The measurement of a PCI, for instance, requires a manual survey and the utilization of the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) guidelines [4]. On the other hand, the LTPP Distress Identification Manual offers comprehensive descriptions of various types of pavement distresses, including cracks, potholes, rutting, and spelling, in both flexible and rigid pavements. Additionally, it provides methods for quantifying these distresses.

Due to the extensive nature of road networks in Europe and the United States, the conventional approach of conducting comprehensive surveys on all existing roadways to assess their rideability and structural integrity is not feasible [5]. Remote sensing methodologies offer valuable resources that can serve as alternatives or complements to existing conventional techniques, thereby addressing a diverse array of requirements in the field of transportation civil engineering.

In addition to the difficulties associated with conducting a comprehensive assessment of the over 6,000,000 km of roads in the United States utilizing point data, there are other factors that restrict the ability to conduct regular, cost-effective, and comprehensive road inspections. Some of the limiting issues are time constraints due to road closures during inspections, potential hazards for inspectors during site work on highways, the need for skilled and experienced inspectors for manual collection methods, and the utilization of destructive tactics [6]. Moreover, the issue of comparison measuring arises due to the descriptive character of several inspections. There are following gaps:

- Currently, asphalt pavement is unable to maintain stability and is prone to deformation as a result of the repetitive impact of heavy traffic. The unstable structure of pavement can lead to several types of failures.
- Road pavements, comparable to other similar infrastructure, require regular maintenance. The utilization of roads for transportation necessitates the consideration of the highway network and its management to ensure a continuous and uninterrupted flow of traffic.
- Road management encompasses various tasks, including the upkeep of pavements. Monitoring the conditions of road pavements during their service life is of utmost importance. The establishment of a suitable Pavement Management System (PMS) is a crucial instrument for road agencies in this context.

The researchers utilized ANN [7], digital twin [8-11], and deep learning [12-13] models to make predictions regarding causalities and PCI to solve the above problems. By utilizing machine learning methods, we can effectively reduce the amount of labor and time required. The existing urban infrastructure within a country plays a crucial role in its overall progress and advancement. Over time, asphalts gradually deteriorate due to the accumulation of traffic and natural conditions. Consequently, the maintenance and repair decisions pertaining to asphalt pose a substantial challenge for road authorities worldwide. In order to overcome this challenge, several road organizations have implemented strategies and protocols to protect their road infrastructure by making timely and suitable maintenance decisions. These practices are typically driven by many circumstances such as lack of information, staffing, money, and lack of expertise.

Dependable and exact evaluation of the current asphalt network condition is a vital part of effective asphalt the board framework. This appraisal has generally been accomplished through a yearly visual asphalt condition review. New innovations are presently accessible to measure other significant asphalt upsets at the organization level. Imaging of the asphalt surface through shooting or on the other hand digitizing and estimating the asphalt profile utilizing non-contact sensors are instances of such advancements. Pavements are major means of highway infrastructure. Maintenance and rehabilitation of these pavements for the required serviceability is a routine problem faced by highway engineers and organizations. Improvement in road management system results in reduction of time and cost, the pavement condition survey plays a big role in the pavement management. The initial phase in setting up a pavement management system (PMS) is road network identification [14]. A vital element of a PMS is the capacity to assess the present condition of a pavement network and anticipation of future condition. The pavement condition and traffic speed are considered as operative and important factors that affect the efficiency of highway systems. The

surface rehabilitation of multilane highways should be awarded a high priority by highway establishments, as this represents an important component of the road network. The main objectives of this investigation are:

- To predict the general scope of IRI values relating to asphalt condition.
- To Assess the pavement performance index
- To establish the most significant factors that influence decision making in Pavement maintenance management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pavement Condition Index (PCI)

The procedure for assessing pavement condition involves the execution of a pavement condition survey and the computation of the PCI. The PCI is a quantitative measure that spans from 0 to 100, where 0 signifies deteriorating pavement and 100 signifies optimal (new) condition. The outcomes of a visual evaluation that determines the categories, quantities, and intensity of unease are utilized to analyze PCI. The purpose of its design was to provide an index that assesses both the structural integrity and surface serviceability of the pavement. The PCI serves as the default condition index for the PAVER system. The selection of the National Highway (N-5) for the research project was based on its national importance, as previously mentioned. The highway serves as a link between Peshawar and Rawalpindi. This route facilitates connectivity between Wah-Cantt, Hassan Abdal, Islamabad, and several other significant urban centers.

An indispensable requirement for any pavement repair and/or management endeavor is a comprehensive understanding of its condition. Consequently, there is a need for a standardized methodology to evaluate the pavement's quality. The assessment of a pavement's state is a prerequisite for making a determination regarding the need for maintenance. The methodology employed for quantifying or evaluating the Pavement Condition Index. The pavement deterioration data for each sample unit was collected directly from the road location for each road segment. The survey data is subsequently computed to determine the PCI value for each unit in the sample. The mean value of a sample within a single PCI unit of a road segment represents the PCI value observed on the evaluated road segments. Each segment's PCI value is calculated as the mean of the values obtained from each sampled unit. The assessment of each segment's condition is determined by interpreting the PCI value obtained from the assessment scale. Two road segments, specifically the second segment with a PCI rating of 37.8 (Poor), and the fourth section with a PCI value of 39.0 (Poor), have been identified as experiencing the most severe conditions. Flowchart illustrating the methodology of whole mechanism as shown in Figure 1.

PCI Rating Determination

Examine the sample unit, ascertain the type and severity of distress, and subsequently quantify the density. The determination of deduct values is based on the deduct value curves associated with each type and severity of distress. The computation of a total deduct value (TDV) involves the summation of all component deduct values. The corrected deduct value (CDV) can be derived using the correction curves after the computation of the TDV. In the process of calculating the CDV, if any individual deduct value exceeds the CDV, the CDV is adjusted to match the highest individual deduct value. The PCI score is calculated using the formula $PCI = 100 - CDV$.

Determination of PCI Rating

Density of the distresses, measured in square metres (m²) or square feet (ft²), is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Distress Amount}}{\text{sample Unit Area}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

And

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{No. of Potholesess}}{s} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Flowchart of Research Methodology

ANN Models

The initial level, known as the Input Layer, is a vector that represents each variable that is input into the computation. The regularization process takes place prior to the inputs being supplied into the input layer in the majority of instances. Because every input will fall within the same range that has been regularized in the past, the ANN will be completely objective. With the retired subcaste (Layer), which is an alternative subcaste, neurons send modified signals from the input subcaste to the affair subcaste after collecting them from the retired subcaste. This occurs after the neurons have collected the signals from the retired subcaste. It is eventually the third sub caste, the affair sub caste, that is responsible for collecting the changed signals from the retired sub caste. This sub caste is also responsible for transforming these signals into the affair vector. Every time a replication takes place, the weights and impulses of every neuron are calibrated based on a number of different criteria. These factors include the literacy algorithm and the literacy rate. It is important to maintain the cost function at the lowest possible level.

RESULTS

Road Section Evaluation of Study Area

Specifically, the travel time study for this project will be conducted on N-5, which is also referred to as Grand Trunk (G.T.) Road. Karachi and Torkham are both connected by a nationally recognized roadway known as the N-5. The length of it is around 1756 kilometers. The N-5 is the longest highway in the country, and it is the one that connects the port city of Karachi to the border crossing at Torkham. There are four provinces that make up its entirety: Punjab (1021 kilometers), Sindh (671 kilometers), Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (127 kilometers), and the Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) (37.5 kilometers). Each of the following sections can be found on the G.T. road, as described below:

- Section 1: Peshawar – Islamabad
- Section 2: Islamabad – Kharian
- Section3: Kharian – Lahore

- Section 4: Lahore – Khanewal
- Section 5: Khanewal – Rohri
- Section 6: Rohri – Karachi

A study is being conducted on Section 1 to 6: Peshawar – Karachi. The PCI is being calculated by using numerical values of various sorts of distress. Additionally, an ANN model is being developed in such a way that it can compute the PCI values. The two results are then compared and studied. The Figure 2 that you see here is a graphical depiction of the learning space [15].

Figure 2. Google Earth Map of the Area

Perform an inspection of the sample unit, identify the type of distress and the level of severity, and then measure the density. The deduct values are derived from the deduct value curves for each type of distress and degree of the distress. To determine the total, deduct value, also known as the TDV, simply add up all of the individual deduct values. The CDV can be calculated using the correction curves once the TDV has been computed. In the process of calculating the CDV, the CDV is equivalent to the highest individual deduct value that is higher than the CDV. This occurs when any individual deduct value is higher than the CDV. Computing the PCI involves utilizing the equation $PCI = 100 - CDV$ as a reference.

Training, Validation & Testing Datasets

For the purpose of the ANN learning (or training) process, this dataset is utilized. The weight and bias vectors are modified in order to lessen the discrepancies that exist between the outputs and the objectives. There are 140 records in this category, which accounts for 70 percent of the total data that was collected, as shown in Figure 3.

This dataset is utilized to monitor the convergence of the ANN education process. Additionally, it is typically utilized to prevent overfitting, which ensures that the ANN model may be applied to additional inputs that go beyond the fundamental data that was used to train or verify it. This dataset contained thirty records, which accounted for fifteen percent of the total data (Figure 4).

The effectiveness of the artificial neural network (ANN) that was trained in the past is evaluated with the help of this dataset. It has no connection whatsoever to the second and third datasets, which are the training and validation datasets. This particular group was provided with the remaining records of the gathered data, which amounted to thirty records in total and included those that were not

utilized in the training or attestation datasets. This represents fifteen percent of the total records, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 3. Training Dataset

Figure 4. Validation Dataset

Figure 5. Testing Dataset

The training procedure reached its maximum limit of 400 epochs. The figures presented in this study display the outcomes for all datasets, including the training, confirmation, and testing datasets. The

findings indicate a clear and consistent pattern, with a pitch value that closely approximates 1.0 across all three groups. This pitch value serves as an indicator of the model's ability to accurately predict the PCI value. The findings additionally indicate that the artificial ANN made two incorrect predictions on the PCI. The training dataset utilized a certain case; however, the testing dataset employed a distinct instance. Further examination of those two occurrences unveiled that the inputs were not faithfully represented in the gathered data.

DISCUSSION

Graphs are used to illustrate the results for all datasets and the three groups (training, validation, and testing datasets). The results indicate a consistent pattern across all three groups, with a pitch value approaching 1.0. This value serves as an indicator of the model's ability to reliably forecast the PCI value. The results additionally indicate that the ANN made two inaccurate predictions for the PCI. The testing dataset contains a case, whereas another instance has undergone the training method. Subsequent examination of the aforementioned scenarios revealed that the inputs were inadequately reflected in the collected data.

The PCI is employed to assess and approximate the current state of pavement conditions by considering the density and degree of distress as observed in real-world scenarios. It is recommended to employ an AI methodology instead of the traditional approach for simulating the intricate relationship between the PCI and other quantifiable attributes, including distress types, severity, and locations, as well as the quantity of manholes within the section. Numerical values are assigned to all types of distress, and ANN modeling is employed to forecast the progression of each distress type. The subsequent slide presents a comprehensive elucidation of the anticipated PCI values, which are contingent upon the severity level of each distress kind. The PCI offers a quantitative assessment of pavement conditions, taking into account the prevailing distresses. To compute PCIs using conventional methods, crucial field data (such as distress kinds and rigidity) is acquired through a visual inspection system. The intricate and demanding process of forecasting the PCI values is facilitated by utilizing the acquired data. The aim of this inquiry is to construct a straightforward and adaptable model that demonstrates the connections between PCIs, types of torments, and stiffness.

The prediction of PCI values for different components is achieved through the utilization of ANN technology, hence obviating the necessity for manual labor and specialized methodologies in estimating PCI values. Moreover, the utilization of ANN enables the integration of novel localized factors, such as the existence of manholes in specific pavement regions. To gain a deeper comprehension of the situation and determine the corresponding PCI values, an assessment was conducted on 150 directional portions from 10 distinct roadways in the city of Peshawar, Pakistan. The ASTM 6433 07. The data indicated a weak and gradual association between PCI and distress, since the highest absolute correlation between PCI and any type and level of distress did not exceed 0.36. The findings demonstrated that the ANN model has a high degree of accuracy in predicting the PCI, as evidenced by the independent R² values of 0.9970, 0.9827, and 0.9955 for the training, validation, and testing datasets, respectively.

CONCLUSION

The PCI is employed to assess and approximate the current state of pavement conditions by considering the density and degree of distress as observed in real-world scenarios. Appropriate quantities of samples are selected for assessment and visual scrutiny. The road segment rating of the National Highway (N-5) has been determined to be "very good," as indicated by an average PCI of 75, with a few samples being assessed as "bad." The present study (PCI) showcases the creation of an artificial intelligence system for the purpose of predicting the Pavement Condition Index (refer to the Graphs of PCI Prediction Using ANN). The database is additionally utilized for the purpose of constructing an ANN model, which is capable of predicting PCI values by utilizing a collection of inputs that provide a description of the roadway section. The tested model exhibits a strong correlation between the observed and expected PCI values, with a pitch value approaching 1.0,

indicating a precise and reliable forecasting model. The association's coefficient of determination was determined to be 0.9971. The Pavement Maintenance Management (1982) serves as a valuable resource for selecting the most appropriate maintenance approach, taking into account the predetermined rating assigned to the pavement portions. This handbook provides a practical maintenance approach for each type of distress at a certain level of intensity.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

All authors thank to the Faculty of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Wuhan University of Technology, Wuhan, Hubei China for providing required facilities for this research.

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